

Spectrophotometric Determination of Uranium(VI) with Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide and Application to Uranium Ores

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The yellow coloured UO_2^{2+} -bis-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complex was extracted in isobutylmethyl ketone from solutions of pH 5.5 to 7.0 and the metal was determined by measuring the absorbance of the extract at 395 nm (for 50–300 μg of U) or at 415 nm (U, above 300 μg) with relative standard deviation of $\pm 1.01\%$. The presence of Ag^+ and Ti^+ did not interfere while magnesium-EDTA was used to mask Pb^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ni^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ce^{3+} , Th^{4+} , VO_2^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} and CrO_4^{2-} . For Co^{2+} , Be^{2+} and Zr^{4+} sulphosalicylic acid was used as the masking agent and iodide for Hg^{2+} . The uranium content of several ores containing 2–25% of this metal has been determined with an average relative error of $\pm 1.3\%$. The dissociation constant of the complex was found to be 1.53×10^{-12} .

SEVERAL β -diketones¹⁻⁵ and related organic reagents with similar reactive groupings^{6,7} have been used for the determination of uranium (VI). Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide⁸ has also been used as a gravimetric reagent for this metal ion. At the time of developing this method⁹ of analysis of uranium (VI), it was observed that the masking of foreign ions are much easier when small amounts of samples are handled, with larger quantities more than two extractions were necessary. This work was undertaken to determine uranium in ores, rapidly by masking various foreign ions present with suitable reagents. Magnesium-ethylenediamine tetraacetate (Mg-EDTA) alone could mask 17 other metal ions.

Experimental

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide solution: The reagent was prepared following the method due to Weissberger et al⁹. A 0.5% solution of the reagent ($1.75 \times 10^{-2} M$) in ethanol was prepared and 2 ml of this was used for each estimation.

Uranium (VI) solution: Uranyl nitrate (E. Merck), was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the metal content was determined gravimetrically^{8,10}. It was diluted to obtain a uranium concentration of 100 μg per ml.

Mg-EDTA solution: For each determination 2 ml of 0.01 *M* Mg-EDTA was used which was obtained by mixing and diluting stock solutions of magnesium sulphate (0.1 *M*) and Na_2EDTA (0.1 *M*).

Pyridine solution: An aqueous 10% solution of distilled pyridine was prepared, stored in coloured bottles. Fresh solutions were prepared every two weeks.

All the chemicals were of A.R. or G.R. grade.

Apparatus: The absorbance measurements were carried out with a Hilger and Watts H-700 Uvispeck Spectrophotometer using 1-cm matched quartz cuvettes. A Cambridge bench model pH-meter was used.

Procedure for uranium (VI): An aliquot of the uranium solution (25–450 μg of U) was taken in a 25 ml beaker, diluted to 10 ml, and heated to 60°–70° on a water bath. Heating was necessary to enhance the rate of the reaction. The reagent solution (1 ml) was added and the pH was raised first to ~4.0 with aqueous ammonia and then adjusted between 5.5–7.0 with a 10% pyridine solution. After cooling to room temperature, it was transferred to a separatory funnel. The beaker was washed with 5 ml isobutylmethyl ketone and the solvent was added to the separatory funnel. After shaking for a few minutes, the aqueous layer was transferred to the beaker, treated with further 1 ml of the reagent solution and 5 ml of extracting solvent as before. The combined methyl isobutyl ketone layer after extraction was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dehydrated with sodium sulphate. The absorbance was measured at 395 or 415 nm against reagent blank within 2 hr. Pure solvent could also be used as reference at 415 nm.

When uranium (VI) was determined in the presence of foreign metal ions, 2 ml of Mg-EDTA solution (0.01 *M*), sulphosalicylic acid (15 mg) solution or potassium iodide (15 mg) solution was added prior to the addition of the reagent.

Procedure for uranium ores: A weighed quantity of the ore (0.2–0.5g) was treated with nitric acid sulphuric acid (1 : 1) mixture and heated to fumes. It was

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cooled, diluted, filtered and the undissolved part was freed from silica with hydrofluoric acid. The residue was fused with potassium bisulphate, extracted with water and mixed with the original filtrate. The combined filtrate was diluted to 500 ml in a volumetric flask.

Uranium was estimated in an aliquot (1.5 ml) of this solution following the procedure described above in the presence of 4 ml of Mg-EDTA (0.01 M), 1 ml of ammonium acetate (5%) solution and 2 ml of sulphosalicylic acid (15 mg) solution, all added before the addition of the reagent solution. Absorbance was measured at 395 nm. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF URANIUM IN ORES

Weight of sample (mg)	U, % Standard method ^{1,2}	U, % Given method	Rel. Error (%)
489.5	2.29	2.24	-2.19
		2.31	+0.87
495.6	8.60	8.57	-0.34
		8.75	+1.74
242.5	24.70	24.74	+0.16
		25.34	+2.60

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves and conformity to Beer's law: From the absorbance curves presented in Figure 1 it is evident that the λ_{max} for this uranium (VI) benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complex in isobutylmethyl ketone lies in the range 385-395 nm with lower concentrations of the metal ion, but shifts slightly to higher wave length with the increase in concentration. However, this did not affect the results much as the peak was more or less flat.

The plots of absorbance against the concentration of uranium (Figure 2) shows that Beer's law is valid upto a maximum concentration of 35 μg of U(VI) per ml of isobutyl methyl ketone when measurements are taken at 395 nm. But at 415 nm the maximum concentration allowed is 45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and as there is no absorbance due to the reagent (Figure 1) pure solvent could be used as reference.

Selection of solvent: Several oxygen containing solvents like diethyl ether, *n*- and iso-amyl alcohol, tributyl phosphate in addition to isobutyl methyl ketone were tried for the extraction. The last mentioned solvent was selected due to relative ease in extraction.

Figure 1. Absorbance curves of uranium (VI)-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide in isobutylmethyl ketone. (a) $[\text{UO}_2^{2+}] = 30 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$; (b) $[\text{UO}_2^{2+}] = 20 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$; (c) $[\text{UO}_2^{2+}] = 15 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$; (d) $[\text{UO}_2^{2+}] = 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$; (e) reagent blank.

Figure 2. : Absorbance of uranium (VI)-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide against concentration.

purification and recovery. The colour of the extract was stable upto 2 hr.

A single extraction with isobutyl methyl ketone could recover 99% of uranium present and the second extraction ensured quantitative transfer.

Optimum pH and reagent concentration : The extraction was found to commence above p^H 3.0 and was quantitative between 5.3 to 7.2, and the range 5.5-7.0 was maintained for safety. A total of 10 mg of the reagent was required for the quantitative complexation and transfer to non-aqueous layer. Larger amounts of it were required when the extraction was carried out with the reagent in isobutyl methyl ketone instead of forming the complex in aqueous solution prior to extraction. As the reagent showed some absorbance at the working wave-length this procedure was not followed.

Nature of the complex : The empirical formula of the U(VI)-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complex was determined by mole-ratio method due to Meyer and Ayres¹¹. A series of solutions were prepared by mixing $0.04 \times 10^{-3} M$ uranium (VI) solution with reagent solution of concentrations varying between $1.75 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $1.05 \times 10^{-1} M$. The p^H was adjusted to 5.5-7.0, the complex was extracted with isobutyl methyl ketone and the absorbance was measured. The plot of absorbance against mole-ratio of ligand to metal indicated the metal to ligand ratio as 1 : 2. The same result was derived by the slope ratio method. The dissociation constant of the complex was found to be 1.53×10^{-12} from the slope-ratio method¹².

Effect of diverse ions : It was observed that uranium (VI) (150 µg) could be determined in the presence of 0.5 mg each of Tl^+ or Ag^+ and at least twenty-one other metal ions provided suitable masking agents were used. Thus, Mg-EDTA could mask 0.25 mg each of Pb^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Ni^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ce^{3+} , Th^{4+} , VO^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} or CrO_4^{2-} and potassium iodide was used for Hg^{2+} (0.25 mg). Similarly sulphosalicylic acid was found to be effective when 0.25 mg of Co^{3+} , Be^{2+} or Zr^{4+} was present. The average relative error for three determinations was $\pm 0.80\%$.

Optimum concentration range and sensitivity : The optimum concentration range for the determination of uranium(VI) is 4.0-13.0 µg per ml (at 395 nm) or 8.0-25.7 µg per ml (at 415 nm) of isobutyl methyl ketone. The Sandell sensitivities (for 0.001 absorbance) are 0.02 (at 395 nm) and 0.04 (at 415 nm).

Molar absorptivity and standard deviation : The molar absorptivity values calculated for 395 nm and 415 nm were $12950 \pm 1.1\%$ and $6514 \pm 0.4\%$. The relative standard deviation was $\pm 1.01\%$ for 46 determinations 150 µg of uranium used.

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